

Cleavage Reactions of some Phenyltin Compounds with Iodine Halides, -Pseudohalides and -Carboxylates

P. C. SRIVASTAVA*, P. SINGH, M. TANGRI, A. SINHA and S. BAJPAI

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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Cleavage reactions of iodinehalides, -pseudohalides IX (X = Cl, Br, NCO, NCS, N₃ and CN) with Ph₃SnCp yield triphenyltinhalides, -pseudohalides (Ph₃SnX) indicating cleavage of Cp-Sn bond in preference to Ph-Sn bond, and cleavage reactions of iodine carboxylates IX' (X' = CH₃OCO, C₆H₅OCO, C₆H₅CH₂OCO, *o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, *o*-ClC₆H₄OCO, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄OCO, *p*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, C₆H₅CH=CHOCO) (*in situ*) with Ph₃SnCl give hitherto unknown diphenylchlorotin carboxylates (Ph₂SnX'Cl) indicating cleavage of Ph-Sn bond in preference to Cl-Sn bond. On the basis of the results, it is predicated that these diphenylchlorotin carboxylates possess bridging carboxylate groups (inter-molecularly chelated structure) in the solid state, whereas in solution they contain chelated carboxylate groups (intra-molecularly chelated structures).

In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report the reactions of iodine halides, -pseudohalides (IX, X = Cl, Br, NCO, NCS, N₃ and CN) with Ph₃SnCp yielding Ph₃Snhalides, -pseudohalides (Ph₃SnX) and the reactions of iodine carboxylates (IX', X' = CH₃OCO, C₆H₅OCO, C₆H₅CH₂OCO, *o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, *o*-ClC₆H₄OCO, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄OCO, *p*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, C₆H₅CH=CHOCO) (*in situ*) with Ph₃SnCl giving diphenylchlorotin carboxylates (Ph₂Sn(X')Cl).

Results and Discussion

The cleavage reactions of Ph₃SnCp with iodine halides and -pseudohalides (IX) (X = Cl, Br, NCO, NCS, N₃ and CN) indicate (i) preferential cleavage of Cp-Sn bond in comparison to Ph-Sn bond and (ii) provide new routes for the synthesis of Ph₃Sn halides and -pseudohalides (Reaction-1). The cleavage reactions of Ph₃SnCl with iodine carboxylates (IX') (X' = CH₃OCO, C₆H₅OCO, *o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, *o*-ClC₆H₄OCO, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄OCO, *p*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, C₆H₅CH=CHOCO) indicate (iii) selective cleavage of one Ph-Sn bond in preference to Cl-Sn bond and (iv) yield hitherto unknown diphenylchlorotin carboxylates (Reaction-2).

These diphenylchlorotin carboxylates are white and brown solids, stable in dry and inert atmosphere. They are sensitive to atmospheric oxygen and moisture and soluble in common organic solvents such as acetone, chloroform, DMSO, THF and nitrobenzene. The molar conductance values (10⁻³M solution in nitrobenzene at 25°) and molecular weights data (determined cryoscopically in the same solvent) indicate monomeric and non-electrolytic nature of the compounds (Table 1).

Ir spectra : The ir data of known Ph₃Sn halides, -pseudo-

halides are well-documented. The characteristic main peaks have, therefore, been listed in Table 2. The ir data for new diphenylchlorotincarboxylates (Table 1) are discussed below. The values of $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{OCO}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{OCO}$ were observed in the range 1540-1590 and 1375-1402 cm⁻¹ respectively. The $\Delta\nu\text{OCO}$ values were in the range 143-210 cm⁻¹. In the (solution) ir spectrum of the representative compound [Ph₂SnCl (*o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO)], $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{OCO}$ increases while $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{OCO}$ decreases to negligible extent.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA FOR DIPHENYLCHLOROTIN CARBOXYLATES*

Compd./ (M p., °C)	Sn% Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. wt. : Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond. Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹
Ph ₂ Sn(CH ₃ COO)Cl (>220)	32.32 (32.38)	365 (367)	3.56
Ph ₂ Sn(C ₆ H ₅ COO)Cl (72)	27.65 (27.70)	366 (429)	7.24
Ph ₂ Sn(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ COO)Cl (48)	26.80 (26.83)	377 (433)	8.85
Ph ₂ Sn(<i>o</i> -NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO)Cl (80)	26.68 (26.77)	428 (444)	8.76
Ph ₂ Sn(<i>p</i> -NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO)Cl (85)	26.72 (26.77)	402 (444)	8.32
Ph ₂ Sn(<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COO)Cl (85)	25.05 (25.07)	388 (474)	9.12
Ph ₂ Sn(<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ COO)Cl (72)	29.54 (29.64)	381 (464)	6.06
Ph ₂ Sn(C ₆ H ₅ CH=CHCOO)Cl (75)	26.04 (26.12)	393 (455)	8.85

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl analyses.

These data coupled with molecular weight measurements indicate bridging carboxylate groups possessing intermolecularly chelated structures in the solution similar

to those observed for dialkyltindiacetates² and dialkylchlorotin carboxylates³.

¹H nmr spectra : In the ¹H nmr spectra of Ph₂Sn(C₆H₅CH₂OCO)Cl, phenyl protons appear at δ 7.15 (m) and CH₂-protons of carboxylate group at 3.48 (s). In the spectra of Ph₂Sn(C₆H₅CH=CHOCO)Cl, the phenyl protons of the carboxylate group appear at δ 7.10 (m), CH protons of the carboxylate group appear as singlet at 7.35 and 7.72 (s) and protons of the phenyl ring attached to Sn at 7.47. The spectrum of Ph₂Sn(*p*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO)Cl shows the phenyl protons of carboxylate group at δ 7.75 ppm, and the protons of the phenyl group attached to Sn at 7.35. In Ph₂Sn(*o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO)Cl, NH₂ protons of the carboxylate group appear as a broad peak at δ 3.25 (br)¹, C₆H₄ protons 7.90 and phenyl protons of the ring attached to Sn at 7.50. The integration of the peak areas corresponds to the proposed composition as diphenylchlorotin carboxylates.

Experimental

Ph₃SnCl (E. Merck), cyclopentadiene (B.D.H.), Ti(I)SO₄ (Fluka) and carboxylic acids (B.D.H.), viz. CH₃COOH, C₆H₅COOH, C₆H₅CH₂COOH, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄COOH, *o*-NH₂-C₆H₄COOH, *o*-Cl-C₆H₄COOH, *p*-NH₂-C₆H₄COOH, C₆H₅CH=CHCOOH were used. CpTi¹, Ph₃SnCp¹, iodine monobromide⁴ and iodine pseudohalides⁵ (generated *in situ*) were prepared by the reported methods. Sodium carboxylates were prepared by the interaction of carboxylic acids with NaOH in distilled water and were used after prolonged drying in a dessicator at room temperature. Iodine carboxylates IX' (X' = CH₃OCO, C₆H₅-OCO, C₆H₅CH₂OCO, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄OCO, *o*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, *o*-ClC₆H₄OCO, *p*-NH₂C₆H₄OCO, C₆H₅CH=CHOCO) were generated (*in situ*) at -10° in a methanol-ice-cold bath.

A typical preparation of C₆H₅CH₂COOI is given below.

To a stirred slurry of C₆H₅CH₂COONa (1.23 g, 7.78 mmol) in CCl₄ (~10 ml) in a methanol-ice-cold bath (-10°) was added slowly a solution of ICl (1.26 g, 7.78 mmol) in the same solvent (~10 ml) over a period of 10–20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for an additional 5–10 min and then filtered to get rid of NaCl. Although C₆H₅CH₂COOI was not isolated from the solutions, but its presence was inferred⁵. Similarly, CH₃COOI, C₆H₅COOI, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄COOI, *o*-NH₂C₆H₄COOI, *o*-ClC₆H₄COOI, *p*-NH₂C₆H₄COOI, C₆H₅CH=CHCOOI were generated (*in situ*) and used as such.

Chlorine was estimated volumetrically by Volhard's method⁶. All the reactions and their work-up were carried out under N₂-atmosphere and physicochemical measurements were done as before¹.

Cleavage reactions of Ph₃SnCl with iodine carboxylates : A typical cleavage reaction of Ph₃SnCl with iodine benzylate is described as follows. A solution of Ph₃SnCl (3.0 g, 7.78 mmol) in CCl₄ (25 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring to a violet solution of C₆H₅CH₂COOI (2.03 g, 7.78 mmol) at ambient temperature (25°). There was no change in the colour of the solution. After addition, the mixture was refluxed for 2 h and the colour changed from violet to light purple. It was filtered, the filtrate concentrated to ~10 ml by distilling off the excess solvent and then distilled at 10 mm Hg to give PhI (0.99 g, 62.36%). To the residue, petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) was added and the resulting solid washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°), crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as light brown solid, dried at 25° (10 mm Hg) and identified as Ph₂Sn(C₆H₅CH₂COO)Cl. Similarly, reactions of Ph₃SnCl with other iodine carboxylates gave Ph₂Sn(X')Cl

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF TRIPHENYL TIN HALIDES AND -PSEUDOHALIDES OBTAINED THROUGH CLEAVAGE REACTIONS OF Ph₃SnCp WITH IODINE HALIDES, -PSEUDOHALIDES IX (X=Cl, Br, N₃, NCS, NCO, CN)

Sl. no.	Reactants	Products*		M.p.** °C	Analysis % : (Found/Calcd.)			
		(g., yield %)			C	H	N	Sn
1.	Ph ₃ SnCp, ICl (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.68, 87.5)	Ph ₃ SnCl (3.12, 80.9)	106 (106–07) ^a	56.00 (56.03)	3.72 3.89	–	30.56 30.87)
2.	Ph ₃ SnCp, IBr (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.66, 86.4)	Ph ₃ SnBr (3.98, 92.5)	117 (121–22) ^b	50.14 (50.23)	3.44 3.49	–	27.60 27.67)
3.	Ph ₃ SnCp, IN ₃ (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.62, 84.4)	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ ^a (3.11, 79.4)	113 (114–15) ^c	55.05 (55.10)	3.78 3.83	10.66 10.71	30.30 30.36)
4.	Ph ₃ SnCp, INCS (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.62, 88.0)	Ph ₃ SnNCS ^b (3.82, 93.6)	175 (174–75) ^d	55.78 (55.88)	3.62 3.68	3.40 3.43	29.10 29.17)
5.	Ph ₃ SnCp, INCO (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.73, 90.1)	Ph ₃ SnNCO ^c (2.82, 71.9)	99 (99) ^e	58.14 (58.16)	3.72 3.83	3.44 3.50	30.24 30.36)
6.	Ph ₃ SnCp, ICN (10 mmol) (10 mmol)	C ₆ H ₅ I, (1.68, 87.5)	Ph ₃ SnCN ^d (2.40, 63.8)	251 (255–56) ^f	60.56 (60.64)	3.92 3.72	3.70 3.72	31.44 31.65)

*Ir spectral data : ^aν_{asym} 2090, ν_{sym} 1332, δ 651 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 7, 8); ^bν_{asym} 2080, ν_{sym} 846, δ 455, ν_{asym} Sn–C(Pb) 260, ν_{sym} Sn–C(Ph) 225 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 9–11); ^cν_{asym} 2225, ν_{sym} 1328, δ 610 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 11–13); ^dν_{asym} 2150 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 10, 13, 14).

**Lit. value in parenthesis : ^aRef. 15; ^bRef. 16; ^cRef. 7; ^dRef. 17; ^eRef. 18; ^fRef. 19.

(Table 1) in 51–79% yields.

Cleavage reactions of Ph₃SnCp with iodine halides and iodine pseudohalides : To a solution of Ph₃CpSn (4.15 g, 10 mmol) in CCl₄ (25 ml) was added a solution of ICl (1.63 g, 10 mmol) in the same solvent (30 ml) dropwise at 60°. The colour of ICl disappeared immediately. The solution was then concentrated by distilling off excess of solvent at reduced pressure (10 mm Hg). It was then distilled at 10 mm Hg to give C₅H₅I (1.68 g, 87.5%). The solid residue was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to obtain Ph₃SnCl as a white solid. Similarly, other cleavage reactions of Ph₃SnCp with IBr and iodine pseudohalides were carried out (Table 2).

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